

Transport for London

Description

A commitment to sharing of open source data by Transport for London has already resulted in over 8,200 developers registering to use data collected by the organisation. As the official body responsible for public transportation in London including bus service and the Underground, open data sharing at Transport for London is based on the belief that as a public agency, the data collected is publically owned and should be accessible in order to capitalise on its use and reuse, with the intent of maximising its value to taxpayers. Transport for London regulates the use of data with certain limitations and restrictions placed on each user and employs license agreements for specific resources like route maps.

Registered data users have created over 500 smartphone apps that enable the public to access transportation information in a quick and efficient manner. Transport for London collects large amounts of data on numerous performance indicators like current service status and service disruptions; timetables and predicted arrival and departure times. The availability of this information to third parties spurs innovation and fuels economic development in the technology sector, while facilitating the creation of small and medium sized businesses in London and beyond.

Economic benefits

Enabling developers to access open source data and build apps that are highly desirable by the public increases efficiency, saves time and requires limited investment by Transport for London. Outsourcing app development saves the organisation money by not investing in an 'in-house' app development team.

The public benefit from significant time savings achieved when planning their travel. Deloitte estimates that these apps saved users time valued between £15 million and £58 million in 2012, all for very little capital investment by Transport for London.

Health/social benefits

The public directly benefit from reduced time spent commuting to work or school, while the apps can reduce vehicle traffic congestion by encouraging more people to use public transportation and by redistributing passenger travel times throughout the day.

Supporting links

'More than 2,000 new developers sign up for TfL's open data in last six months'

<http://bit.ly/TFL-open-data>

Accessed 28 April 2016.

'United Kingdom's Transport for London'

<http://bit.ly/UK-TFL>

Accessed 07 May 2016.

'Transport for London, developers, and open data'

<http://bit.ly/TFL-developers>

Accessed 07 May 2016.

'TfL to expand open data sharing'

<http://bit.ly/TFL-expand-open-data>

Accessed 07 May 2016.